

1 **Thermodynamic analysis of experimental sorption isotherms of loquat and quince**
2 **fruits**

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6 **Abstract**

7 Sorption isotherms of loquat and quince fruits were determined by static gravimetric
8 method at different temperatures, in the range from 20 to 65°C. The curves obtained can
9 be considered as type II at 20°C and type III at higher temperatures according to the
10 Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) classification. Equilibrium moisture content data were
11 correlated by different mathematical models usually applied to foodstuffs (GAB, Peleg
12 and Halsey). The best fit of the experimental data was obtained with Peleg and GAB
13 models. Experimental data were analysed by a thermodynamic approach to obtain such
14 properties as net isosteric heat, net equilibrium heat, differential and integral entropy
15 that provide a deeper understanding of the properties of water and energy requirements
16 associated with sorption process. Particularly, for loquat and quince fruits, the
17 differential enthalpy and entropy decreased with increasing moisture content and
18 satisfied the compensation theory. The net integral enthalpy show maximum values (32,
19 26, 24 kJ/mol for loquat pulp, loquat seeds and quince, respectively) and the net integral
20 entropy has the opposite behaviour with minimum values (-90.8, -70.8, -68.1 J/mol K
21 for loquat pulp, loquat seeds and quince, respectively) at specified moisture contents.

22 Keywords: water activity; equilibrium moisture content; isosteric heat; equilibrium heat.

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28 Nomenclature

		Units
A_m	Area of a water molecule	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-19} \text{ m}^2$
a	Halsey parameter (Eq. 2)	–
a_w	Water activity	–
C	GAB (Eq. 1) parameter	–
E	Mean relative percentage deviation modulus (%)	–
E_{RMS}	Root mean square error	–
G	Free Gibbs energy	kJ/mol
H	Enthalpy	kJ/mol
K	GAB (Eq. 1) parameter	–
K_B	Boltzmann's constant	$1.38 \cdot 10^{-23} \text{ J/K}$
m_1, m_2	Peleg (Eq. 3) parameters	–
N	Number of samples	–
n	Number of isotherms	–
n_1, n_2	Peleg (Eq. 3) parameter	–
Q	Heat of sorption	kJ/mol
q	Net heat of sorption	kJ/mol
R	Ideal gas constant	8.314 J/mol K
R^2	Coefficient of regression	–
r	Halsey (Eq. 2) parameter	–
S	Entropy	J/mol K
T	Absolute temperature	K
X	Equilibrium moisture content	kg water/kg d.b.
X_M	GAB (Eq. 1) parameter	kg water/kg d.b.

Subscript

cal	Calculated
d	Differential
eq	Equilibrium
exp	Experimental
hm	Harmonic mean
I	Isokinetic
L	Water condensation
M	Monolayer
N	Multilayer
O	Pre-exponential
st	Isosteric

Greek letters

φ	Spreading pressure	J/m^2
Δ	Difference	

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39 **1. Introduction**

40 Loquat is an edible fruit (*Eriobotrya japonica* Lindl.) belonging to the Rosaceae family
41 (Badenes et al., 2000). Its reported composition (wet basis) refers water 78.0%,
42 carbohydrates 10.6%, fiber 10.2%, fat 0.5%, protein 0.4% and other components 0.3%
43 (Mataix et al., 1998). The world production of loquat in 2006 is estimated at 550,000 t
44 (Lin, 2007; Soler et al., 2007).

45 Quince (*Cydonia Oblonga* Mill) belongs to the pome fruit family. The main constituents
46 of quince are water 84% and carbohydrates 15% (wet basis). Other small constituents
47 include proteins 0.4% and fats 0.6%. It is also considered a good source of fiber,
48 potassium and vitamin C. The world production of quince in 2006 is estimated at
49 490,000 t (FAO, 2007).

50 The difficulties of hand harvesting and the damage during transport limit the
51 commercial expansion of edible fruits as quince and loquat. Data on moisture content
52 and water activity is important to predict the physical, chemical and biological changes
53 occurring during storage and processing of food materials. The water sorption isotherm
54 represents the equilibrium relationship between moisture content of the food sample and
55 water activity at constant temperature and pressure. Food systems typically exhibit Type
56 II and III (according to the BET classification, Brunauer et al., 1940) isotherms.
57 Knowledge of the sorption isotherm of food materials is very important for prediction of
58 quality and optimization of the drying, storage and other processes. Three models (GAB
59 (Van den Berg and Bruin, 1981), Halsey (Halsey, 1948) and Peleg (Peleg, 1993)) were
60 employed for fitting results. This work was developed due to absence of experimental
61 data on sorption isotherms of loquat and quince fruits.

62 Further analyses of the sorption phenomena can be undertaken in terms of
63 thermodynamic functions. The thermodynamic properties of food provide an

64 understanding of water properties and energy requirements associates with the sorption
65 behaviour. In the literature, thermodynamic functions for analysis of sorption behaviour
66 include differential enthalpy and entropy, and integral enthalpy and entropy.

67 Differential enthalpy of sorption is used as an indicator of the binding strength of the
68 water to the solid. Knowledge of the differential heat of sorption is of a great
69 importance when designing equipment for dehydration processes. This is due to the fact
70 that the heat of vaporization of sorbed water may increase to values above the heat of
71 vaporization of pure water as food is dehydrated to low moisture levels (King, 1968).

72 Differential entropy of a material is proportional to the number of available sorption
73 sites corresponding to a specific energy level. The isokinetic or enthalpy–entropy
74 compensation theory has also been used to evaluate sorption processes. This states that
75 compensation arises due to changes in the nature of the solvent-solute interaction, and
76 that a linear relationship exists between the reaction enthalpy and entropy, and the
77 corresponding slope represents the isokinetic temperature. The isokinetic temperature
78 represents the temperature at which all reactions in series proceed at the same rate.

79 Integral enthalpy provides an indication of the total energy available to do work, and
80 has some relationships with the energy balance of drying and freezing operations (Gal et
81 al., 1975). Integral entropy describes the degree of disorder and randomness of motion
82 of water molecules. It is a measurement of the mobility of the adsorbed water
83 molecules, and indicates the level to which water/substrate interaction is greater than the
84 interaction between water molecules.

85 The objectives of the present work are to (i) provide experimental data for the sorption
86 characteristics of loquat and quince fruits; (ii) model the sorption isotherm using
87 selected equations; (iii) determine the thermodynamic properties, and (iv) evaluate the
88 application of the enthalpy-entropy compensation theory to the sorption phenomena.

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90 **2. Materials and methods**

91 *2.1. Preparation of samples*

92 Loquat and quince were purchased from a local market; pieces were selected according
93 to its size and ripeness. The quince was peeled and cut into thin slabs of about 3 mm.
94 The loquat was peeled, the seeds were carefully separated from the pulp and their peel
95 was also removed, both pulp and seeds were cut into thin slabs (3 mm).

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97 *2.2. Determination of sorption isotherms*

98 The equilibrium moisture contents of loquat and quince were determined by a
99 gravimetric technique, which is based on the use of saturated salt solutions to maintain
100 constant water activity at determined values of the samples when equilibrium is reached
101 between atmosphere and food sample food. The salt solutions used to obtain constant
102 relative humidity of surrounding air were KOH, LiCl, MgCl, K₂CO₃, Mg(NO₃)₂,
103 NH₄NO₃, NaCl, KCl and BaCl₂ which were prepared according to recommendations
104 (Greenspan et al., 1977); this group of salts allows to obtain a wide range of relative
105 humidity of air from 7 to 91 %RH in equilibrium.

106 The determination of sorption isotherms for loquat pulp and seeds and quince pulp was
107 carried out in the same range of temperatures from 20 to 65°C. The temperatures studied
108 for the loquat samples were 20, 35, 50 and 65°C while for the quince fruits were 20, 45,
109 and 65°C.

110 In order to inhibit microbial growth a small quantity of thymol was also placed in the
111 flasks in which water activity was greater than 0.5. Triplicate samples of 2 g were
112 placed on Petri dishes inside the jars. Samples were weighted at regular intervals until
113 constant weight (± 0.0005 g) in an analytical balance (Mettler AJ150). The equilibrium

114 period was about 8 weeks. The moisture content was determined using a vacuum oven
115 (Heraeus Vacutherm VT 6025) at 70°C and 13 kPa, achieving constant weight after
116 three days (A.O.A.C., 1995).

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118 2.3. Data analysis

119 2.3.1. Sorption isotherm models

120 The sorption isotherm represents the moisture content variation with water activity,
121 which is defined as the ratio between vapor pressure of water in the food surface and
122 vapor pressure of pure water at the same temperature.

123 The sorption isotherm models used to fit experimental data are collected in Table 1 (Eq.
124 (1) to (3)). The parameters of the models used were estimated by non-linear regression
125 procedure employing Table Curve software (Jandel Scientific), in order to select the
126 best correlation and to improve the analysis of the experimental data. The goodness of
127 the fitting of each sorption model to the experimental equilibrium moisture content and
128 water activity data was evaluated based on statistical parameters like coefficient of
129 determination (R^2), mean relative percentage deviation modulus (E) and root mean
130 square error (E_{RMS}).

$$131 \quad E = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|X_{\text{exp}} - X_{\text{cal}}|}{X_{\text{exp}}} \quad (4)$$

$$132 \quad E_{RMS} = \left[\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_{\text{exp}} - X_{\text{cal}})^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

133 In the GAB (Guggenheim-Anderson-de Boer) model there are three parameters (C, K,
134 and X_M), which are functions of temperature and can be associated some physical
135 meanings, where X_M accounts the monolayer moisture content, C is a constant related to
136 heat of sorption of the first layer and K is related to the heat of sorption of the

137 multilayer. The influence of temperature on GAB parameters C, K and X_M can be
 138 calculated by Arrhenius equations (Kim and Bhowmik, 1994):

$$139 \quad X_M = X_{M0} \exp(\Delta H/RT) \quad (6)$$

$$140 \quad C = C_0 \exp[(H_M - H_N)/RT] \quad (7)$$

$$141 \quad K = K_0 \exp[(H_L - H_N)/RT] \quad (8)$$

142 where H_L is the average heat of condensation of water vapor (43.14 kJ/mol in the
 143 investigated range of temperature from 20 to 65°C). The heats H_M , H_N and ΔH were
 144 determined by fitting of the equations (6), (7) and (8) after fit of the experimental data
 145 values to the GAB model to obtain the corresponding three-parameters (C, K, and X_M).

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147 *2.3.2. Differential enthalpy and entropy*

148 The differential enthalpy, often referred to as isosteric heat of sorption, is an indicator of
 149 the state of water absorbed by the solid material. The isosteric heat of sorption (Q_{st}) is
 150 defined as the net isosteric heat of sorption plus the heat of vaporization of water at the
 151 system temperature (Tolaba et al., 2003).

$$152 \quad Q_{st} = q_{st} + H_L \quad (9)$$

153 The net isosteric heat of sorption (q_{st}) for specific moisture content was calculated from
 154 the experimental data using the Clausius-Clapeyron equation (Tsami, 1991):

$$155 \quad q_{st} = -R \left[\frac{d \ln(a_w)}{d(1/T)} \right]_X \quad (10)$$

156 The net isosteric heat of sorption was calculated from the slope after plotting $\ln a_w$
 157 versus $1/T$ at constant moisture content. This approach assumes that isosteric heat of
 158 adsorption can be considered constant with temperature and requires measurements of
 159 the sorption isotherms at more than two temperatures.

160 The differential entropy (S_d) of adsorption can be calculated from Gibbs-Helmholtz
161 equation as follows:

$$162 \quad S_d = \frac{Q_{st} - G}{T} \quad (11)$$

163 Substituting the free Gibbs energy by its definition equation, Eq. (12), a new equation
164 (13) that relates Q_{st} , S_d and a_w is obtained:

$$165 \quad G = RT \ln(a_w) \quad (12)$$

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$$167 \quad \ln(a_w) \Big|_X = \frac{Q_{st}}{RT} - \frac{S_d}{R} \quad (13)$$

168 By plotting $\ln(a_w)$ against the inverse of temperature, at constant moisture content, the
169 S_d can be easily determined from the intercept (S_d/R).

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171 *2.3.3. Enthalpy-entropy compensation theory*

172 Enthalpy-entropy compensation theory or isokinetic relationship is used to evaluate
173 physical and chemical phenomena that prevail in the sorption processes. This theory
174 proposes a linear relationship between Q_{st} and S_d (Leffer and Grunwald, 1963):

$$175 \quad Q_{st} = T_I S_d + G \quad (14)$$

176 Plotting Q_{st} against S_d , isokinetic temperature (T_I) and the free energy (G) at T_I can be
177 calculated using linear regression. T_I represents the temperature at which all reactions in
178 the sorption series proceed at the same rate. Krug et al. (1976) recommended a test for
179 the compensation theory, which involves the evaluation of the isokinetic temperature
180 respect to the harmonic mean temperature T_{hm} , which is defined as:

$$181 \quad T_{hm} = \frac{n}{\sum_{i=1}^n (1/T)} \quad (15)$$

182 where n is the number of isotherms.

183 The compensation theory only can be applied if $T_1 \neq T_{hm}$. If $T_1 > T_{hm}$ the process is
 184 enthalpy driven, while if the opposite condition is observed, the process is considered to
 185 be entropy controlled.

186

187 2.3.4. Integral enthalpy and entropy

188 The net integral enthalpy, or net equilibrium heat of sorption (q_{eq}), represents the total
 189 energy available to do work. It is calculated in a similar manner to the differential heat
 190 of sorption, but at constant spreading pressure instead of constant moisture content
 191 (Rizvi, 1986).

$$192 \quad q_{eq} = -R \left[\frac{d \ln(a_w)}{d(1/T)} \right]_{\phi} \quad (16)$$

193 A plot of $\ln(a_w)$ against $1/T$ at constant spreading pressure gives the net integral
 194 enthalpy from the slope. The variation in net integral enthalpy with moisture content
 195 indicates the level to which water/substrate interactions is greater than the interactions
 196 of water molecules (Fasina et al., 1999).

197 The spreading pressure is the force applied in the plane of the surface that must be
 198 exerted perpendicular to each unit length of edge to keep the surface from spreading.

199 This parameter is not subject to direct experimental measurement; it can be estimated
 200 using an analytical procedure when to be used the empirical relationship between
 201 moisture content and water activity (Smith et al., 2001).

202 Halsey equation (Eq. 2) was used to obtain the parameters a and r , which are used in the
 203 following equation that defines the spreading pressure.

$$204 \quad \phi = \frac{K_B T}{A_m} a^{1/r} \left[\frac{1}{\left(\frac{1}{r} - 1 \right) (-\ln(a_w))^{\frac{1}{r}-1}} \right]_{0.05}^{a_w} \quad (17)$$

205 Net integral entropy describes the degree of disorder and randomness of motion of
206 water molecules and is given by (Mazza and Le Maguer, 1978):

$$207 \quad S_{\text{eq}} = \frac{-q_{\text{eq}}}{T} - R \ln(a_w) \quad (18)$$

208 where a_w is the water activity obtained at constant spreading pressure at different
209 temperatures.

210

211 **3. Results and discussion**

212 *3.1. Fitting of sorption models to experimental data*

213 Figure 1 (a, b, c) shows the experimental data of equilibrium sorption isotherm for
214 quince, loquat pulp and loquat seed, respectively, at different temperatures.

215 As expected, the equilibrium moisture content increased with water activity at constant
216 temperature. These changes in equilibrium moisture content are due to the tendency of
217 the food material to lower vapor pressure when decreasing the relative humidity of air.

218 A more detailed data analysis lead to the identification two different regions in the
219 isotherm curves, at low and intermediate water activities, the so-called multilayer
220 sorption region, moisture content increases linearly with water activity, whereas at high
221 water activity levels, the so-called capillary condensation region, water content rapidly
222 increases with water activity. Falade and Aworh (2004) explains this behaviour based
223 on changes in sugar state, at low water activity it is possible to have a local dissolution
224 of sugar alcohols, in the intermediate water activity range there is gradual dissolution of
225 sugars resulting in a complete exudation of sugars in solution at high water activities.

226 There is also an increase in moisture content with decreasing temperatures, at constant
227 water activity. This can be explained because at higher temperatures, the activation of
228 the water molecules changes to higher energy levels and the links become less stable
229 and break away from the water-binding sites of food material, consequently the

230 equilibrium moisture content decreases (Palipane and Driscoll, 1992). The increase of
231 temperature has also an important effect on chemical and microbiological reactions
232 relative to the spoilage. The temperature influences the physicochemical properties of
233 fruits, which in turn reduces the number of active sites for water binding.

234 According to the BET classification (Brunauer et al., 1940) the sorption curves obtained
235 are type II at 20°C and type III at higher temperatures.

236 An interesting phenomenon was observed when Fig. 1 (a, b) are analysed. Moisture
237 sorption isotherm curves of quince are lower than those of loquat fruit in all the range of
238 temperatures. This means that quince fruit presents lower strength in holding water in
239 comparison with loquat pulp. This behaviour is also observed when comparing
240 experimental data of loquat and quince pulp with seeds (Fig. 1b and 1c), in this case the
241 sorption isotherm curves of seeds are the lowest by its composition as was expected.

242 The coefficients of the three sorption models tested at different temperatures were
243 obtained, and shown in Table 2. These models showed high coefficients of
244 determination ($R^2 > 0.961$), acceptable standard error ($E < 16.9\%$) and low root mean
245 square error ($E_{RMS} < 0.126$). These results indicate that all the models can be considered
246 as acceptable for predicting the equilibrium moisture content of these fruits. However,
247 the Peleg (Eq. 3) and the GAB (Eq. 1) models (four- and three-parameters, respectively)
248 were found to have the lowest standard error and the highest coefficient of
249 determination (R^2) and additionally the behaviour of the residue have checked, this
250 behaviour shows random residues in all cases.

251 The sorption equilibrium moisture isotherms of quince pulp and loquat pulp and loquat
252 seeds using the GAB model, are plotted in Fig. 1 (a, b, c). It can be observed a good
253 quality of fitting. A correlation of the GAB model parameters X_M , C , and K with
254 temperature was established. The monolayer moisture content X_M is the minimum

255 moisture content covering hydrophilic sites on the material surface, and it is a necessary
256 data for achieving storage with minimum quality loss for long time. Furthermore, at this
257 condition, the rates of spoilage reactions, except for oxidation of unsaturated fats, are
258 minimal. Therefore, at a given temperature, the safest water activity level is that
259 corresponding to X_M or lower. Estimated values for X_M value are within the reported
260 values for fruits, which vary between 4% and 15% (dry basis) (Kiranoudis et al., 1993;
261 Moraga et al., 2006). Rizvi (1986) noted that monolayer moisture content decreases
262 with temperature increases. This behaviour has been ascribed to a reduction in the
263 number of active sites due to physical and chemical changes induced by temperature.
264 The values of C and K parameters are also within the reported limits for fruits.
265 A more detailed analysis of the GAB parameters can provide further valuable
266 information. The value of (H_M-H_N) represents the difference in enthalpy between
267 monolayer and multilayer sorption, and (H_L-H_N) represents the difference between the
268 heat of condensation of water and the heat of sorption of the multi-layer (Van den Berg
269 and Bruin, 1981). The values of C_0 , K_0 , X_{M0} , (H_M-H_N) , (H_L-H_N) and ΔH evaluated with
270 Eqs. (6), (7) and (8) are showed in Table 3. They agree with the literature data for other
271 food materials (Goula et al., 2008).
272 The values of (H_M-H_N) and (H_L-H_N) indicate how strong water molecules are bound in
273 the respective layers. The estimated (H_M-H_N) values have positive values as expected,
274 due to the strong exothermic interaction of water vapor with primary sorption sites of
275 the material. The (H_L-H_N) values are smaller and positives which is in agreement with
276 the literature (Samaniego-Esguerra et al., 1991; Tsami et al., 1990).
277 The modified Halsey model became the moisture sorption isotherm equation that is
278 used in determining the water activity for further thermodynamic analysis.
279

280 3.2. Thermodynamic properties

281 3.2.1. Differential enthalpy and entropy

282 The net isosteric heat of sorption, so-called differential enthalpy, can be determined by
283 means of the fitting with Eq. (10) of water activity data versus temperature, obtained
284 from sorption isotherms. The results are shown in Fig 2. They are similar to those
285 presented by Quirijns et al., (2005), who reported maximum values of net isosteric heat
286 for different food product, from 23 kJ/mol for carrot to 52 kJ/mol for potato.

287 Curves in Fig. 2 clearly illustrate an exponential decrease in the net heat of sorption
288 with moisture content increases. At high moisture content the net heat of sorption
289 approaches to zero, meaning that the value of the heat of sorption is the same than the
290 heat of vaporization of water. Similar effects of moisture content on the net heat of
291 sorption were reported by Tsami (1991) for dried currants, figs, prunes, and apricots,
292 Telis et al., (2000) for persimmon skin and pulp, Al- Muhtaseb et al., (2004) for starch
293 powders and Kaya and Kahyaouglu (2007) for tarragon and safflower petals. The
294 physical explanation for the rapid increase in q_{st} at low moisture contents may be that in
295 the initial stages of sorption there are highly active polar sites on the surface of the food
296 material, which are covered with water molecules to form a monomolecular layer, the
297 amount of energy required to remove these water molecules, tightly bounded to the
298 food, is very high. As the moisture content increases the strength of water molecules
299 bounds decreases such as the net isosteric heat of sorption.

300 Isosteric heat of sorption (Q_{st}) was determined using Eq. (9), below the moisture content
301 of 0.1 kg water/kg d.b. for loquat seeds and 0.3 kg water/kg d.b. for loquat and quince
302 pulp, the values for the sorption net isosteric heats increase significantly. These results
303 indicate that at lower moisture content the isosteric heat of sorption starts to differ
304 (approximately 20%) from the latent heat of vaporization of pure water.

305 The change in the values of the heat of sorption with moisture content regarding to the
306 latent heat of vaporization of pure water, provides valuable data for energy consumption
307 calculations and subsequent design of drying equipment (McMinn and Magee, 2003).

308 As it is known, sorption entropy is proportional to the number of available sorption sites
309 at a specific energy level, and the corresponding values can be calculated using Eq. (13)
310 at different moisture contents. The results obtained are shown in Fig 3. In this figure it
311 can be observed the strong dependence of differential entropy on moisture content with
312 an exponential trend similar to the behaviour exhibited for the differential enthalpy.
313 These results are in agreement with literature data (Al-Muhtaseb et al., 2004; Kaya and
314 Kahyaouglu, 2007 and Goula et al., 2008).

315

316 *3.2.2 Enthalpy-entropy compensation theory*

317 Plotting differential enthalpy versus differential entropy a linear correlation is found.
318 This means that the theory of compensation could be applied in the range of moisture
319 contents studied. The results were correlated according to Eq. (14) and the isokinetic
320 temperature of sorption was calculated as $T_I = 368$ K for quince and 359 K and 364 K
321 for the pulp and the seeds of loquat, respectively. These values are in the range of data
322 reported in literature (Goula et al., 2008; Al-Mahasneh et al., 2007). The compensation
323 theory can be applied if the calculated harmonic mean temperature (T_{hm}) is significantly
324 different from T_I . The harmonic mean temperature was calculated by Eq. 15 and the
325 obtained results are $T_{hm} = 312$ K for quince and for pulp and seeds loquat is 315 K, as
326 these values are significantly different from the value of T_I , the suitability of the
327 isokinetic theory is confirmed and, additionally, as in all cases $T_I > T_{hm}$, the processes
328 can be characterized as enthalpy driven.

329 The compensation theory fulfilment implies that only one mechanism of reaction is
330 followed by all members of the reaction series, the existence of only one mechanism
331 suggests that the microstructure of the foods is stable and does not suffer any changes
332 during moisture sorption (McMinn et al., 2005).

333

334 *3.2.3. Integral enthalpy and entropy*

335 The spreading pressure was calculated using the Eq. 17 and the values obtained, at
336 different temperatures, of quince and loquat are plotted in Fig. 4. The results indicate
337 that the spreading pressure increases with water activity, and decreases with
338 temperature, at a given water activity. The values for spreading pressure, and trends
339 with respect to temperature and water activity, are comparable to those reported for
340 melon seed and cassava (Aviara and Ajibola, 2002), and for safflower petals and
341 tarragon (Kaya and Kahyaoglum, 2007).

342 The net integral enthalpy at each spreading pressure was obtained by fitting Eq. (18) to
343 the equilibrium data, plotting $\ln(a_w)$ versus $1/T$ for a specific spreading pressure; q_{eq} was
344 determined from the slope. The variation in net integral enthalpy with the moisture
345 content for quince and loquat is shown in Fig. 5, at lower moisture content the enthalpy
346 increase until maximum values (32, 26 and 24 kJ/mol) at moisture contents (0.11, 0.06
347 and 0.1 kg water/kg d.b.) for loquat pulp, loquat seeds and quince, respectively, and
348 below these values decreased. The physical explanation of this behaviour may be that at
349 low moisture contents water is absorbed on the most accessible locations on the surface
350 area of the solid. The increase of moisture content possibly caused swelling of material
351 and then new high energy sites are opened and new water binding can be developed.
352 This behaviour explains the increasing of the net integral enthalpy at low moisture
353 contents. The decreasing of the net integral enthalpy may be explained by the fact that

354 less favorable locations are covered with water molecules, forming multiple layers of
355 sorbed water. Similar trend have been reported for cassava (Aviara and Ajibola, 2002),
356 potato (McMinn and Magee, 2003) and safflower petals and tarragon (Kaya and
357 Kahyaoglu, 2007). Another important fact is that the moisture content where the
358 maximum integral enthalpy is reached is nearly close to monolayer moisture content
359 value obtained from the GAB model (Eq.1). A similar behaviour is reported by Kaya
360 and Kahyaoglu (2007), which explain that around monolayer moisture content, water is
361 more tightly bound than the rest of water adsorbed in other regions of the isotherms.

362 The net integral entropy (S_{eq}) was calculated by applying the same equation Eq. (18),
363 but using the intercept. The variation in net integral entropy with moisture content for
364 quince and loquat is shown in Fig 6. The values were negative in magnitude, the same
365 as Iglesias et al. (1976), which attribute negative entropy values to the existence of
366 chemical adsorption and/or structural modifications of the adsorbent. The net integral
367 entropy values of loquat pulp, loquat seeds and quince decrease at low moisture
368 contents reaching a minimum value (-91, -71 and -68 J/mol K at different moisture
369 contents of 0.11, 0.06 and 0.1 kg water/kg d.b., respectively), and then increased as
370 water covers the surface and forms further layers. Similar trends have been reported in
371 literature for soya bean (Aviara et al., 2004), cassava (Aviara and Ajibola, 2002), and
372 for safflower petals and tarragon (Kaya and Kahyaoglu, 2007). At low water activity
373 range, a decrease in the net integral entropy values is possibly caused by localization of
374 water (loss of rotational freedom and degree of randomness) due to the strongest
375 binding sites with water molecules and solid as suggested by McMinn and Magee
376 (2003). The minimum integral entropy can be interpreted as the water activity at which
377 the product has the best stability of a food product (Nunes and Rotstein, 1991;
378 Domínguez et al., 2007).

379

380 **4. Conclusions**

381 The results of sorption isotherms and thermodynamic analysis obtained for both fruits
382 are different, but analogous. This was expected since each food is a complex
383 combination of various constituents, which not only can sorb water independently but
384 can also interact among themselves.

385 The moisture sorption isotherms of quince and loquat can be described as belonging to
386 the type II at 20°C and type III at higher temperatures according to the Brunauer–
387 Emmett–Teller (BET) classification. An increase in temperature caused a decrease in
388 the amount of adsorbed water for the same water activity. This indicates that the quince
389 and loquat becomes less hygroscopic materials at higher temperatures.

390 After testing five equations describing moisture sorption isotherm in the temperature
391 range investigated (20-65°C), the kinetic three-parameters GAB model and the
392 empirical four-parameters Peleg equation were found the best correlations for the
393 experimental sorption data for quince and loquat throughout the range of water activity
394 studied (0-0.9).

395 The isosteric heat of sorption was high at low moisture contents decreasing with
396 moisture content increases; the trend is to reach the latent heat of vaporization of pure
397 water at higher moisture content. The differential entropy has an analogous behaviour to
398 the isosteric heat. The plot of isosteric heat versus entropy data satisfies the enthalpy-
399 entropy compensation theory.

400 Net integral enthalpy increases with moisture content up to achieve a maximum value
401 and then decreases. In a reverse way, integral entropy decreases with moisture content
402 to a minimum value and then increases.

403

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407

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508

509 **Captions for Figures**

510

511 Fig. 1a, b, c. Experimental data of equilibrium moisture contents of quince and loquat
512 pulps and loquat seeds. Lines correspond to the GAB model (Eq. 1).

513

514 Fig. 2. Effect of moisture content on the net isosteric heat of sorption for quince and
515 loquat pulps and loquat seeds.

516

517 Fig. 3. Variation of differential entropy with moisture content quince and loquat pulps
518 and loquat seeds.

519

520 Fig. 4. Variation of spreading pressure with moisture content and temperature for
521 quince and loquat pulps and loquat seeds.

522

523 Fig. 5. Variation of integral enthalpy with moisture content quince and loquat pulps and
524 loquat seeds.

525

526 Fig. 6. Variation of integral entropy with moisture content quince and loquat pulps and
527 loquat seeds.